

Impact of groundwater solutes on the fate and reactivity of nanoscale iron nitride particles

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ABSTRACT

Partial or full nitriding of nanoscale zero-valent iron (nZVI) particles suppresses their corrosion and enhances their selectivity for chlorinated ethenes. However, the impact of groundwater solutes on the reactive lifetime of Fe_xN-based nanoparticles remains poorly understood. Herein, we aged Fe_xN nanoparticles for 30 days in suspensions containing realistic concentrations of common groundwater solutes and characterized the resulting transformation products. Subsequently, the aged particles were exposed to trichloroethene (TCE) to evaluate reactivity changes under varying water chemistries. Acquired results demonstrate that aged Fe_xN nanoparticles effectively degrade TCE across a range and concentrations of groundwater solutes, including Na⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Cl⁻, SO₄²⁻ and HCO₃⁻. The primary corrosion products in these solutions were “white rust” and “green rust” minerals. Variations in TCE dechlorination rates were linked to the type and concentration of solutes, pH, and the resultant corrosion products. Notably, TCE degradation was significantly suppressed in the presence of HPO₄²⁻ and NO₃⁻ ions, with vivianite and magnetite being the dominant corrosion products, respectively. Findings from single salt experiments were validated using two groundwater samples. This study elucidates the complex effects of solutes on Fe_xN corrosion and reactivity, providing valuable insights for predicting the performance of Fe_xN-based materials in groundwater remediation.

1. Introduction

Nanoscale zero-valent iron (nZVI) has been extensively studied over the past two decades as a promising agent for the reductive in situ remediation of groundwater contaminants [1–3]. Despite their widespread commercial application, nZVI particles are known to be negatively influenced by their high reactivity with water and other natural reducible species, leading to their rapid corrosion and limited longevity under field conditions [4,5]. Various strategies to improve the performance of nZVI have been investigated, including doping with catalytic metals [6,7], coating with organic polymers [8–10], immobilization in solid porous materials [11,12] and sulfidation, which currently represents the most accepted approach [13–16]. Recently, the nitriding of (n) ZVI (i.e., formation of crystalline iron nitride, Fe_xN, phases from the

nZVI precursor) has been proposed as a highly promising route to further improving the reactive lifetime and selectivity of iron-based (nano)particles for target contaminants [17–19].

Fe_xN and mixed-phase Fe_xN/ZVI nanoparticles (NPs), which have been investigated for contaminant removal, were synthesized using two methods: the reaction of gaseous ammonia with nZVI at elevated temperatures (i.e., gas nitriding) [17,19] and by a sol-gel synthesis using gelatin as a nitrogen source followed by pyrolysis [18]. Crystalline Fe_xN phases were found to increase the particle hydrophobicity as well as corrosion resistance, which provides better surface availability of iron in reduced forms and facilitates electron transfer toward adsorbed contaminants [17,18]. Accordingly, such NPs exhibited a 20–30 times higher reduction rate of trichloroethene (TCE) and substantial suppression of hydrogen evolution/corrosion compared to unmodified

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nZVI. The reported reactivity and selectivity of Fe_xN-based NPs for chlorinated ethenes was even higher than that of sulfidated nZVI (S-nZVI), in particular for tetrachloroethene and *cis*-1,2-dichloroethene [17–19]. NPs with a high γ -Fe₄N phase content were also able to rapidly dechlorinate TCE even after being aged for ~100 days under dynamic conditions (125 rpm), showing a 43% drop in their reducing capacity and only a 2.5-fold decrease in the TCE reduction rate compared to fresh Fe_xN NPs [17]. In contrast, pristine nZVI particles underwent surface passivation during the same aging period, which inhibited their reactivity with both water and TCE. The longevity of γ -Fe₄N-containing NPs was thus similar to that of S-nZVI, which lost ~50% of its reducing capacity after being statically aged for 120 days [20]. It should be noted that the depletion of S-nZVI reducing capacity is expected to occur faster under dynamic aging conditions applied for the aging of Fe_xN NPs [17].

The highly promising dechlorination performance of Fe_xN-based NPs for groundwater remediation has been demonstrated in experiments conducted in ultrapure or moderately hard water. To ensure efficient removal of contaminants by these particles under realistic *in situ* conditions, the impact of the groundwater chemistry on the particles' fate and reactive lifetime calls for comprehensive understanding. Previous studies conducted with granular ZVI [21–24], microscale ZVI [25–27], nZVI [28–34] and S-nZVI [35,36] showed that common groundwater solutes may affect the particles' performance. This can be attributed to (i) the promotion of particle corrosion processes, (ii) the formation of complexes or precipitates on the particle surface that lead to surface passivation, and (iii) the modification of the particle adsorption and agglomeration properties by alternating the surface charge and particle magnetic moment. Moreover, reactive solutes such as NO₃⁻ may undergo redox reactions with the particles, resulting in (i) competition for the reactive sites with the target contaminants, thus depleting the particles' reducing capacity, and/or (ii) rapid surface passivation [21,28,31,32, 35,37]. The effect of groundwater solutes was found to depend on their concentration and exposure duration.

Meng et al. reported that TCE degradation by fresh mixed-phase Fe_xN/ZVI NPs dropped substantially in groundwater compared to ultrapure water, while the corrosion rate of NPs, measured as the hydrogen evolution rate, was suppressed in both types of water [18]. This suggests that the Fe_xN-based NPs may maintain high electron efficiency and reactive lifetime in natural groundwater, even though their reaction with target contaminants will not be as fast as in solute-free water. This may even prove advantageous for the remediation of contaminant plumes, where a slow contaminant dissolution into groundwater occurs. However, due to the relatively short (48 h) experiment duration in the study by Meng et al. [18], the long-term effects of groundwater solutes on the corrosion and reactivity of Fe_xN-containing NPs remain unclear.

This study addressed these knowledge gaps, aiming to systematically investigate the influence of common inorganic groundwater solutes on the transformation and reactive lifetime of Fe_xN-based NPs. The specific objectives were to (i) evaluate the effect of common solutes (Na⁺, Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, Cl⁻, SO₄²⁻, HCO₃⁻, NO₃⁻ and HPO₄²⁻) on the corrosion processes of Fe_xN-containing NPs across a range of concentrations occurring in groundwater, (ii) investigate how these transformations affect the TCE removal, and (iii) compare the effects of groundwater solutes on the Fe_xN performance with existing data for pristine nZVI and S-nZVI. To this end, suspensions of Fe_xN NPs were aged for 30 days in various concentrations of single salts. To determine whether the effects of individual solutes observed in single-salt systems were valid for the real environment, analogous experiments were carried out in two different groundwater samples. The aged NPs were characterized using X-ray diffraction (XRD) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and their reactivity was studied in batch experiments with TCE. The presented findings can be used as a reference for predicting the fate and performance of Fe_xN-based NPs in the remediation of groundwater contaminated with chlorinated hydrocarbons.

2. Materials and methods

All preparations for the aging experiments, the reactivity experiments and the sample characterizations were performed in an N₂-filled glove box (O₂ <0.1 ppm) unless specified otherwise. Commercially available nZVI particles (NANO FER 25 P [38]) were purchased from NANO IRON (Židlochovice, Czech Republic). A detailed list of chemicals and reagents used in the experiments is provided in the [Supplementary Information \(SI; Text S1\)](#). Ultrapure water (UPW) with a resistivity of $\geq 18 \text{ M}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$ at 25 °C, prepared by the Simplicity UV system (Millipore® SAS, France), was used for the preparation of single salt solutions in the aging and reactivity experiments. Two groundwater samples were used for evaluation of their influence on the fate and reactivity of the Fe_xN NPs. One groundwater sample met drinking water quality standards and contained HCO₃⁻ and Mg²⁺ as dominant solutes (further referred to as GW_{HCO₃⁻}). The second groundwater sample contained HCO₃⁻, SO₄²⁻, Cl⁻ and Ca²⁺ as prevailing ions. This groundwater sample was collected in an area with intensive agricultural activities, resulting in a high NO₃⁻ concentration of 2.6 mM (further referred to as GW_{NO₃⁻}). A more detailed description of the characteristics and composition of the collected groundwater samples, description of the sampling sites and the composition of bedrock are included in the SI ([Table S1](#) and [Text S2](#)). All single salt solutions and collected groundwaters were sparged with N₂ for 45 min to remove O₂ prior to conducting the experiments.

2.1. Synthesis of Fe_xN nanoparticles

Fe_xN NPs were synthesized by ammonia gas nitriding following a method described in [39], with some minor modifications to maximize the γ -Fe₄N phase content. Briefly, 100 g of nZVI particles were treated by passing anhydrous NH₃/N₂ mixture at a temperature of 430 °C and a pressure of 0.5 bar in a fluid laboratory furnace for 3.5 h. The prepared pyrophoric Fe_xN NPs were then transferred into an air-tight container and stored under an inert atmosphere inside an N₂-filled glove box prior to the use.

2.2. Aging of Fe_xN nanoparticles and TCE dechlorination experiments

In order to investigate the influence of common groundwater solutes on the transformation and reactivity of Fe_xN NPs, we adopted a similar approach as previously described by Mangayayam et al. who studied the effects of groundwater solutes on S-nZVI [35]. The ions tested in our study included Na⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Cl⁻, SO₄²⁻, HCO₃⁻, NO₃⁻ and HPO₄²⁻, with Cl⁻ and Na⁺ serving as counter-ions due to their minimal impact on the reactivity and surface transformations of nZVI. The concentration ranges of the ions used correspond to the typical concentrations of these solutes in natural and agriculture-impacted groundwaters and are in line with previous literature evaluating the performance of nZVI-based materials in groundwater cleanup [28,32,35]. The aging and dechlorination experiments were carried out in 120 mL serum crimp bottles. First, 90 mL of deoxygenated solutions containing common groundwater solutes at varying concentrations ([Table S2](#)) or collected groundwater ([Table S1](#)) were introduced into the serum bottles. Fe_xN NP stock suspension (20% w/w) in UPW was dispersed using a T25 ULTRA-TURRAX® disperser (IKA, Germany) at 11 000 rpm for 2 min, and was subsequently added to deoxygenated solutions to obtain a NP concentration of 0.5 g/L. The serum bottles were then capped with FEB-faced chlorobutyl-isoprene septa, taken out of the N₂-glove box and aged for 30 days under dynamic conditions (horizontal shaker, 125 rpm, 22 ± 1 °C) to accelerate the interactions between the NPs and the solutes. All single salt experiments and experiments in groundwater samples were carried out at least in five replicates: at least two for the TCE degradation experiments and three for the NP characterizations and the measurements of the solution pH. The reference particle aging experiments were performed in UPW in parallel in eight replicates, five of them for the TCE degradation experiments to provide robust reference data. The solution pH was

measured before adding the Fe_xN NPs as well as after 30 days of aging after the removal of the suspended NPs with a strong magnet.

The dechlorination experiments with the aged suspensions were initiated by spiking 90 µL of TCE stock solution in methanol to obtain an initial TCE concentration of 30 mg/L. The spiked serum bottles were then placed back on a horizontal shaker (125 rpm, 22 ± 1 °C). Aliquots of 9 mL were periodically withdrawn from the suspensions for the following 48 h using a needle and syringe. The NPs were separated in the collected samples using a magnet, and the remaining solution was filtered with a 0.1 µm PTFE syringe filter pre-conditioned with methanol. Finally, 7 mL of the filtered solution was transferred into a 20 mL GC headspace amber vial, and the TCE concentration was determined using a headspace 7890B gas chromatograph (GC, Agilent Technologies, USA). Details of the instrumental analysis are summarized in the SI (Text S3). To account for the TCE losses due to the aliquot removal, TCE concentrations in the reaction experiments were normalized to those in the control samples with no added NPs, according to [35]. The observed pseudo-first-order TCE degradation rate constants, k_{obs} , were calculated by least-squares linear fitting using the natural logarithm of normalized TCE concentration as a function of reaction time, as previously used in ref. [35].

2.3. Characterization of Fe_xN nanoparticles

The phase composition of the fresh and the aged NPs was analyzed using XRD with an Aeris diffractometer (Malvern PANalytical, UK) operating in Bragg-Brentano geometry. The diffractometer was equipped with a CoK α radiation source, fixed divergence and diffracted beam anti-scatter slits, and a PIXcel detector. The patterns were measured in the 2 θ range from 5 to 105°, and the data were processed using HighScore Plus software in conjunction with the PDF-4+ and ICSD databases. The quantitative phase analysis was performed using the Rietveld refinement [40].

The particle-size and morphology of the NPs was examined by SEM using a JSM-7900F Jeol scanning electron microscope with an accelerating voltage of 5 kV. To verify the composition of the transformation products, selected samples of the aged NPs were characterized by Energy Dispersive Spectrometry (EDS) using a Jeol JED-2300 SDD detector operated at an accelerating voltage of 15 kV with an acquisition time of 60 s. Additionally, the fresh Fe_xN samples as well as selected samples of the aged NPs were characterized in detail using a transmission electron microscope (TEM) JEOL 2100 at an electron acceleration voltage of 200 kV.

The Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) specific surface area of the fresh NPs was determined using a NOVA 2000e Surface Area Analyzer (Quantachrome, U.S.A.) by multipoint BET analysis of the nitrogen adsorption data at the relative pressure of 0.05–0.3 at –196 °C. The point of zero charge (PZC) of the fresh Fe_xN NPs was determined using a ZetaSizer Nano (Malvern Instruments, UK).

The total Fe content in the fresh Fe_xN NPs was determined on an HCl-digested sample using an inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer 7700x ICP-MS (Agilent Technologies, Tokyo, Japan), fitted with an ASX-520 autosampler, a MicroMist concentric nebulizer, a cooled Scott-type double pass spray chamber, and an octopole reaction cell operating in Helium mode to overcome spectral interferences. The optimized ICP-MS conditions are summarized in Table S3. The total N content was determined on a dry and homogenized sample using an Elemental Vario MACRO CHNS analyzer (Germany). The reducing capacity of Fe_xN NPs was determined by measuring the volume of hydrogen produced after adding an excess of 1:1 mixture of HCl (36%) and UPW to the NP suspensions [17]. A detailed description of the sample preparations for individual techniques and further information are provided in the SI (Text S4).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characteristics of fresh Fe_xN nanoparticles

The fresh Fe_xN NPs consisted almost exclusively of the γ' -Fe₄N phase (>95 wt%), with traces of ϵ -Fe_{2–3}N and metallic α -Fe (Fig. S1 and Table S4). Electron microscopy images revealed that the NPs had irregular spherical shapes and formed aggregates (Fig. S2). The size of individual NPs was ~72 nm (Fig. S3), which was consistent with the size of the precursor nZVI particles before nitriding [38]. The BET specific surface area of Fe_xN was 25.4 m² g⁻¹. The NPs contained 93 wt% of iron and 4.5 wt% of nitrogen, with the remaining amount corresponding mostly to oxygen. The reduction capacity of Fe_xN NPs, expressed as the Fe⁰ content, was 57.4%. The characteristics of the fresh Fe_xN NPs align with those of the “ γ' -Fe_xN” NPs prepared in our previous study [17].

3.2. Particle aging and reactivity in ultrapure water

The Fe_xN NPs were aged for 30 days in UPW to serve as a reference for elucidating the effects of common groundwater solutes. An XRD analysis revealed no significant decrease in the abundance of the γ' -Fe₄N phase after aging (Fig. 1A, Table S4), which is in line with the high corrosion resistance of γ' -Fe₄N NPs reported in our previous study [17]. The two corrosion products detected by XRD in low quantities, representing approximately 2.4% and 1.8% of crystalline phases, were the carbonate green rust trébeurdenite, [Fe₄²⁺Fe₂³⁺(OH)₁₂][CO₃] \cdot 2.9 H₂O, further referred to as GR_{CO3}, and siderite (FeCO₃). GR_{CO3} is a commonly reported iron corrosion product in anoxic carbonate-containing waters [41]. Although no carbonate was added to the UPW in this experiment, CO₂ absorption from the surrounding air likely resulted in small amounts of dissolved carbonate in the aqueous matrix. Additionally, SEM images revealed that the surface of the aged Fe_xN NPs was covered with thin flaky structures (Fig. S4). These structures are characteristic of white rust (Fe(OH)₂), which is a primary product of iron corrosion in water [42]. Fe(OH)₂ was not discernible in the XRD pattern, most likely due to its poorly crystalline nature.

The aged Fe_xN NPs exhibited sustained reactivity in the TCE reduction. The fitted pseudo-first-order rate constant of 29.0 \times 10⁻³ hr⁻¹ (Table S2 and Fig. S5) reached the same order of magnitude as that of the fresh γ' -Fe_xN NPs reported previously (k_{obs} = 74.6 \times 10⁻³ hr⁻¹) and was remarkably similar to the rate of TCE degradation by γ' -Fe_xN NPs aged for three months in moderately hard water (k_{obs} = 28.0 \times 10⁻³ hr⁻¹) [17]. The modest decrease in the NP reactivity upon aging can be attributed to (i) a slower electron transfer to TCE due to a thicker layer of passivating iron (oxyhydr)oxides on the surface of the aged NPs [43,44] and (ii) the agglomeration of the NPs during aging [17,44].

3.3. Effects of dissolved anions

The influence of the common groundwater anions Cl⁻, SO₄²⁻, HCO₃⁻, HPO₄²⁻ and NO₃⁻ on the fate and reactivity of Fe_xN NPs is discussed individually for each ion, where Na⁺ served as the counter-ion for all the tested salts.

3.3.1. Chloride

The exposure of the Fe_xN NPs to varying concentrations of Cl⁻ resulted in only slight surficial corrosion, similar to that of Fe_xN aged in UPW. The intensity of the γ' -Fe₄N peaks in the XRD pattern did not change substantially after 30 days of aging (Fig. 1A). According to the Rietveld refinement, the aged NPs retained 93–96 wt% of γ' -Fe₄N (Table S5). White rust (Fe(OH)₂), exhibiting characteristic thin flakes covering the NP surface (Fig. 1B), was the main observed corrosion product in the 1 mM Cl⁻ solution. At higher Cl⁻ concentrations, GR_{CO3} was detected in low quantities (<5 wt% of crystalline phases) (Fig. 1A and Table S5). Similar to the reference experiment in UPW, the presence of carbonate in the aqueous matrix likely originated from CO₂

Fig. 1. Characteristics of Fe_xN NPs aged in NaCl and Na₂SO₄ solutions of varying concentrations: (A) XRD patterns of NPs aged in Cl⁻ solutions, (B) SEM image of NPs aged in 1 mM Cl⁻, (C) TCE reduction rate constants for NPs aged in varying Cl⁻ concentrations, (D) XRD patterns of NPs aged in SO₄²⁻ solutions, (E) SEM image of NPs aged in 5 mM SO₄²⁻, (F) TCE reduction rate constants for NPs aged in varying SO₄²⁻ concentrations. GR_{CO3}: carbonate green rust, GR_{SO4}: sulfate green rust, WR: white rust, S: siderite.

absorption from the surrounding air, which was not completely removed by purging the solutions with N₂. In addition to iron-containing phases, trace levels of ammonium chloride (NH₄Cl) were also identified by XRD in all samples. Although NH₄Cl is highly soluble in water under ambient conditions, it apparently precipitated on the surface of the aged NPs during the sample preparation, i.e., by freezing the collected solid samples from the aged suspensions. The presence of ammonia can be explained by its leaching from the Fe_xN NPs during aging [17], as shown in Eqs. 1 and 2.

Aging in the 1 mM Cl⁻ solution preserved more effectively the Fe_xN

reactivity with TCE, compared to aging in UPW, with a $k_{\text{obs}} = 47.9 \times 10^{-3} \text{ hr}^{-1}$ (Fig. 1C, Table S2, and Fig. S4). This observation aligns with the higher reactivity reported for S-nZVI particles aged in Cl⁻ solutions with TCE [35,36], as well as with the higher degradation rates of hexachlorobenzene and 4-chloronitrobenzene by (n)ZVI in the presence of dissolved Cl⁻ [21,32]. However, only modest improvement in reactivity was observed with respect to aging in UPW at higher Cl⁻ concentrations. This may be explained by the increasing pH of the Fe_xN suspensions with higher Cl⁻ concentrations (ranging from 8.9 to 9.6, see Table S2), since the rate of TCE dechlorination by (n)ZVI is known to decrease as the pH increases [45,46]. While the different pH values cannot be inherently attributed to the varying Cl⁻ concentrations, Cl⁻ ions have been found to promote pit corrosion of the nZVI surface [21, 32,47,48], which leads to faster OH⁻ production during iron anaerobic

corrosion in water and thus to an increase in the pH (Eq. 3) [49]. The promoted corrosion also resulted in faster leaching of ammonia from the Fe_xN NPs, as described above in Eqs. 1 and 2, which contributed to the pH increase.

3.3.2. Sulfate

The aging of the Fe_xN NPs in SO₄²⁻ solutions slightly enhanced corrosion, as evidenced by the lower amount of a retained γ-Fe₄N phase in the XRD pattern (about 90 wt% based on the Rietveld refinement) (Fig. 1D and Table S5). White rust was the primary corrosion product

when Fe_xN underwent aging in 0.5–2 mM SO₄²⁻ solutions, and it was apparently more abundant compared to Fe_xN aged in UPW and Cl⁻ solutions, based on the XRD pattern (Fig. 1D). Additionally, GR_{CO3} was identified as a minor aging product of the Fe_xN in the 0.5 mM SO₄²⁻ solution. However, with increasing SO₄²⁻ concentrations, GR_{CO3} was no longer apparent but the abundance of sulfate green rust (Fe₂²⁺Fe₃³⁺(SO₄)_{0.5}(OH)₆(H₂O)₄), further referred to as GR_{SO4}, increased (Fig. 1D, Table S5). GR_{SO4} formed typical hexagonal plate-like crystals, which were well visible amid thin flakes of white rust (Fig. 1E). The presence of S in these crystals was confirmed using EDS (Fig. S6). The faster corrosion of the Fe_xN NPs in SO₄²⁻ solutions observed in this study, as evidenced by the lower γ-Fe₄N phase content and higher abundance of corrosion products, is consistent with previous reports that studied

Fig. 2. Characteristics of Fe_xN NPs aged in NaHCO₃ and Na₂HPO₄ solutions of varying concentrations: (A) XRD patterns of NPs aged in HCO₃⁻ solutions, (B) SEM image of NPs aged in 10 mM HCO₃⁻, (C) TCE reduction rate constants for NPs aged in varying HCO₃⁻ concentrations, (D) XRD patterns of NPs aged in HPO₄²⁻ solutions, (E) SEM image of NPs aged in 5 mM HPO₄²⁻, (F) TCE reduction rate constants for NPs aged in varying HPO₄²⁻ concentrations. GR_{CO3}: carbonate green rust, CV: chukanovite, S: siderite, V: vivianite.

the effects of SO_4^{2-} on the corrosion of pristine and sulfidated (n)ZVI [21, 35].

The TCE reduction rates of the Fe_xN NPs aged in SO_4^{2-} solutions were similar to those aged in UPW (Fig. 1F, Table S2, and Fig. S5), with a lower rate constant observed at the highest (5 mM) SO_4^{2-} concentration. Similar trends have been observed previously for TCE degradation by (n) ZVI and S-nZVI [28,35,50], and have been ascribed to a larger extent of nZVI corrosion in SO_4^{2-} solutions. The pH values in the SO_4^{2-} solutions after aging with the Fe_xN were comparable to those in the Cl^- solutions (8.9–9.2, Table S2), suggesting that the slower TCE degradation could also be partly due to the increased pH that resulted from iron oxidation and the leaching of N in the form of ammonia (Eqs. 1–3).

3.3.3. Hydrogen carbonate

The exposure of the Fe_xN NPs to HCO_3^- solutions substantially promoted corrosion, with the $\gamma\text{-Fe}_4\text{N}$ phase content decreasing from 90% to 60% of the crystalline phases as the HCO_3^- concentrations increased (Fig. 2A and Table S5). Fe_xN corrosion was accompanied by the formation of large precipitates, the morphology of which differed with varying HCO_3^- concentrations. The aging of Fe_xN in 1 mM and 4 mM HCO_3^- solutions led to the formation of GR_{CO_3} as the only corrosion product apparent in the XRD patterns. In the solution containing 10 mM HCO_3^- , the dominant corrosion product was chukanovite ($\text{Fe}_2(\text{CO}_3)(\text{OH})_2$), whereas GR_{CO_3} was less abundant (Table S5). SEM images of Fe_xN NPs aged in 10 mM HCO_3^- revealed both the presence of hexagonal sheets characteristic of GR_{CO_3} (Fig. 2B) [41,51] and rhomboidal sheets characteristic of chukanovite (Fig. S7) [52]. These basic iron carbonates are common iron corrosion products in environments with high carbonate concentrations, alkaline pH and anoxic conditions [35,41,51, 53]. Chukanovite was preferentially formed in the 10 mM HCO_3^- solution due to the higher HCO_3^- concentration and the slightly higher pH value (9.7 ± 0.01) [53], compared to less concentrated HCO_3^- solutions (9.3–9.5, Table S2).

Interestingly, the Fe_xN NPs aged in the HCO_3^- solutions exhibited higher reactivity with TCE than those aged in UPW (Fig. 2C, Table S2 and Fig. S5), and the observed TCE degradation rate constants increased with higher HCO_3^- concentrations despite the rise in the pH levels. This trend may be explained by the different surface charge of GR_{CO_3} and chukanovite, as compared to white rust [35,54–56]. The basic iron carbonates are dominantly deprotonated at the measured pH (PZC \approx 8), while white rust remains protonated (PZC \approx 12). As the surface of the Fe_xN NPs is deprotonated at the tested pH (PZC \approx 6.7, Figure S8), basic iron carbonates and Fe_xN may interact to a lesser extent with each other, which leads to weaker interactions and slower aggregation, thereby conserving reactive sites on the Fe_xN surface. A similar trend in TCE reduction has been previously observed for S-nZVI aged in HCO_3^- solutions, where the PZC of FeS surface sites was around 7.5 [35]. Additionally, green rust minerals might also directly contribute to TCE reductive dechlorination, although this reaction is disputed in the literature [57–59].

3.3.4. Hydrogen phosphate

The aging of the Fe_xN NPs in the HPO_4^{2-} solutions led to the massive precipitation (3.6–22.6 wt%) of the iron phosphate mineral vivianite ($\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2 \cdot 8 \text{H}_2\text{O}$), which was the only corrosion product identified by XRD (Fig. 2D and Table S5). The formation of vivianite has been previously observed when pristine nZVI and S-nZVI were aged in phosphate-rich waters [28,31,35]. SEM images revealed that vivianite formed distinct crystals within NP aggregates (Fig. 2E). Additionally, the surface of the aged Fe_xN NPs was covered with thin flakes characteristic of white rust. An EDS analysis confirmed high P abundance in vivianite crystals and, conversely, low P abundance on the surface of the NPs that were far from the vivianite crystals (Fig. S9).

The exposure of the Fe_xN to HPO_4^{2-} negatively impacted the TCE removal (Fig. 2F, Table S2, and Fig. S5), with k_{obs} values being about 50% lower compared to that of Fe_xN aged in UPW. A significant

suppression effect of HPO_4^{2-} has been observed previously for TCE, trichlorobenzene, nitrobenzene and arsenic removal by other (n)ZVI-based materials [23,28,35,61,62]. The passivation by HPO_4^{2-} can be explained by its strong adsorption on the surface of the NPs in the form of inner-sphere $=\text{FePO}_4$ complexes and co-precipitation of iron phosphate minerals during Fe_xN corrosion at basic pH values, both of which effectively block the surface active sites and prevent their interaction with contaminants [28,60–62]. However, the low solubility of phosphate minerals (<0.3 mg/L, i.e., 0.0031 mM) typically results in negligible HPO_4^{2-} concentrations in groundwater [72]. Therefore, strong inhibition by HPO_4^{2-} is not expected in groundwaters except for sites heavily contaminated with fertilizers [35]. Interestingly, the level of Fe_xN passivation after 30 days of aging in the HPO_4^{2-} solutions was lower than that observed for S-nZVI, which lost around 80% of its reactivity when aged at the same HPO_4^{2-} concentrations for 7 days [35]. This indicates that the Fe_xN NPs were able to retain higher reactivity in phosphate-impacted waters compared to S-nZVI.

3.3.5. Nitrate

Fe_xN aged in NO_3^- solutions underwent extensive corrosion, with most of the $\gamma\text{-Fe}_4\text{N}$ phase being converted into stoichiometric magnetite ($\text{Fe}^{2+}\text{Fe}^{3+}_2\text{O}_4$, cell parameter 0.8405–0.8404 nm for 2 and 5 mM, respectively) at NO_3^- concentrations ≥ 2 mM (Fig. 3A and Table S5). Magnetite was present in the form of spherical NPs overgrowing Fe_xN aggregates, as revealed by SEM (Fig. 3B) and TEM (Fig. 3C). These observations indicated that Fe_xN reacted with NO_3^- , as evidenced by the rapid decrease in NO_3^- concentrations in aged suspensions (Fig. S5). At the lowest tested concentration of 0.5 mM, NO_3^- was completely reduced to ammonia by the Fe_xN NPs within one hour. However, at higher NO_3^- concentrations of 2 and 5 mM, only partial NO_3^- reduction to NO_2^- and ammonia occurred, with minimal changes in concentrations after one hour, suggesting that the Fe_xN NPs quickly underwent passivation (Fig. S10). Accordingly, TEM images confirmed the extensive overgrowing of Fe_xN with tiny magnetite NPs already within the first 24 h of aging in 5 mM NO_3^- (Fig. S11). The morphology of such Fe_xN NPs strongly resembled that of nZVI aged under oxic conditions for the same period of time [63]. It should be noted that at NO_3^- concentrations 2 mM and 5 mM, NO_3^- was in excess (1.2 and 3.1 times, respectively) to the Fe_xN reducing capacity, assuming the complete reduction of NO_3^- to NH_4^+ . Nevertheless, Fe_xN did not undergo complete oxidation as substantial amounts (30–35.5 wt%) of the $\gamma\text{-Fe}_4\text{N}$ phase were still detectable in the XRD patterns even after 30 days of aging (Fig. 3A and Table S5). These results indicate that the exposure of Fe_xN to excess NO_3^- led to surface passivation, further inhibiting the electron transfer from the uncorroded Fe_xN core through a dense layer of magnetite nanocrystals on their surface. These findings align with the rapid surface passivation of (n)ZVI particles by NO_3^- reported previously [28,31,32, 64]. The reduction of NO_3^- by Fe_xN was accompanied by a significant increase in the pH to values around 10 (Table S2) owing to the H^+ consumption during the reaction [65].

The removal of TCE by Fe_xN NPs aged at NO_3^- concentrations ≥ 2 mM was strongly suppressed (Fig. 3D, Table S2 and Fig. S5). At these NO_3^- concentrations, Fe_xN NPs quickly underwent surface passivation, with the accessibility of the reactive sites being strongly diminished due to both surface oxidation and the overgrowing of the Fe_xN NPs with magnetite nanocrystals (Figs. 3B and 3C). As discussed above, the aged NPs did not react with TCE, but the slight decrease in TCE concentrations can be attributed to the sorption of TCE onto Fe_xN NPs and their corrosion products. The observed TCE reduction rate constant at the lowest NO_3^- concentration of 0.5 mM was comparable that of the Fe_xN NPs aged in UPW. However, the TCE concentration decreased only during the first 24 h of experiment and later remained constant (Fig. S5), indicating passivation of the Fe_xN particles after this period. It is noteworthy that the S-nZVI particles aged at the same NO_3^- concentrations were able to maintain their reactivity with TCE despite substantial Fe^0 corrosion, suggesting that S-nZVI may be more resistant to surface

Fig. 3. Characteristics of Fe_xN NPs aged in NaNO₃ solutions of varying concentrations: (A) XRD patterns of NPs aged in NO₃⁻ solutions, (B) SEM image of NPs aged in 2 mM NO₃⁻, (C) TEM image of a Fe_xN NP aged in 5 mM NO₃⁻, (D) TCE reduction rate constants for NPs aged in varying NO₃⁻ concentrations. GR_{CO3}: carbonate green rust, M: magnetite, S: siderite.

passivation than Fe_xN NPs in the presence of NO₃⁻ ions [35]. However, due to the shorter aging time of S-nZVI in the study by Mangayayam et al. (7 days), compared to the aging time of Fe_xN in this study (30 days), this assumption requires further validation. It is also important to note that in pristine groundwater, the NO₃⁻ concentrations are typically <0.014 mM, whereas concentrations >0.05 mM (tested in this study) are associated with fertilizer application above or upstream of the aquifer [73]. Therefore, the observed inhibition of Fe_xN NP reactivity is thus relevant only for fertilizer-impacted groundwater.

3.4. Effects of dissolved cations

The effects of various concentrations of Na⁺, Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ cations on the fate and reactivity of the Fe_xN NPs were studied independently in separate solutions. Given that the influence of Na⁺ on the reactivity of nZVI-based NPs was reported in the literature as negligible, e.g., [21, 28], this section focuses primarily on the effects of divalent cations.

3.4.1. Calcium

After 30 days of aging in solutions of varying Ca²⁺ concentrations, the Fe_xN NPs still contained 97.4–98.2 wt% γ-Fe₄N (Fig. 4A and Table S6), suggesting a high corrosion resistance in Ca²⁺-rich waters. Besides γ-Fe₄N and metallic iron (α-Fe), only trace amounts of NH₄Cl were detected by XRD. As previously described, the presence of crystalline NH₄Cl likely stemmed from the sample preparation, i.e., its precipitation during the freezing of collected solid samples. SEM images of the aged Fe_xN (Fig. 4B) further revealed that the NPs were covered with thin flakes resembling in morphology to white rust. However, no white rust has been detected by XRD due to its low abundance and/or

not sufficiently crystalline nature. The pH values in the aged suspensions (9.0–9.4, Table S2) were higher than in UPW and comparable to those in the NaCl solutions, suggesting that the presence of Ca²⁺ only slightly promoted the corrosion of the Fe_xN NPs [66].

Compared to aging in UPW, the aging of the Fe_xN in the Ca²⁺ solutions had only a marginal effect on the TCE reduction rates (Fig. 4C, Table S2, and Fig. S5). Although the reduction rates were slightly higher for the Fe_xN aged in the presence of Ca²⁺, the differences were not significant, and there was no clear reactivity trend that correlated with the varying Ca²⁺ concentrations. The subtle positive effect of Ca²⁺ can be attributed to the promoted Fe_xN corrosion that de-passivated the oxidized surface sites or the salting-out effect of Ca²⁺ that decreased the solubility of TCE and, hence, enhanced its adsorption to the NPs [66,67]. Both the slight activation and the slight inhibition of the TCE degradation after aging in Ca²⁺ solutions have been previously reported for S-nZVI [35,36].

3.4.2. Magnesium

The Fe_xN NPs aged in the Mg²⁺ solutions reached a slightly higher extent of corrosion compared to the Fe_xN aged in the Ca²⁺ solutions. Based on the Rietveld refinement, the γ-Fe₄N phase content in the aged NPs decreased to 86.4–90.2 wt% (Table S6). Several corrosion products were identified using XRD, in particular, akaganeite (β-FeOOH) and white rust (Fig. 4D). Traces of GR_{CO3} and NH₄Cl were also found in some samples. A SEM image revealed extensive overgrowth of the Fe_xN NPs by irregular sheets ascribed to white rust, alongside with larger sheets ascribed to akaganeite (Fig. 4E). The faster Fe_xN corrosion in the presence of Mg²⁺ compared to UPW or the Ca²⁺ solutions is consistent with previous literature documenting enhanced Fe⁰ corrosion in Mg²⁺-rich

Fig. 4. Characteristics of Fe_xN NPs aged in CaCl₂ and MgCl₂ solutions of varying concentrations: (A) XRD patterns of NPs aged in Ca²⁺ solutions, (B) SEM image of NPs aged in 5 mM Ca²⁺, (C) TCE reduction rate constants for NPs aged in varying Ca²⁺ concentrations, (D) XRD patterns of NPs aged in Mg²⁺ solutions, (E) SEM image of NPs aged in 5 mM Mg²⁺, (F) TCE reduction rate constants for NPs aged in varying Mg²⁺ concentrations. GR_{CO₃}: carbonate green rust, WR: white rust, AG: akaganeite, S: siderite.

waters [26,68]. This was interpreted as the result of lower pH of the ZVI suspensions in Mg²⁺ solutions compared to the particle suspensions in other common inorganic salts, thus facilitating Fe⁰ corrosion. The decrease in the pH was ascribed to proton release after the formation of the =FeOMg⁺ surface complex [26]. The trend toward decreasing pH values as Mg²⁺ concentrations increased (pH 8.7–8.1) was also apparent in this study (Table S2).

The increased Fe_xN corrosion in the presence of Mg²⁺ had a slightly inhibitive effect on the TCE reduction rates when compared to that in UPW (Fig. 4F, Table S2, and Fig. S5). This may be attributed to the high extent of surface coverage by white rust in the Mg²⁺ solutions, whose positive surface charge may have facilitated interactions and agglomeration with the negatively charged active sites of the Fe_xN (PZC of white rust and Fe_xN are 12.1 and 6.7, respectively). However, this effect

was small, partly due to the lower pH of the suspensions, which in turn may have had a positive effect on the reactivity of the Fe_xN NPs. The Mg²⁺ solutions were previously found to have a positive effect on the reactivity of S-nZVI with TCE [35,36]. While the mechanism has yet to be studied in greater detail, the improved reactivity of S-nZVI was likely due to the enhanced surface depassivation, as observed for the aged ZVI [26,68].

3.5. Particle aging and reactivity in real groundwater

To assess whether the longevity of the Fe_xN NPs in real groundwater, containing mixtures of different solutes, can be inferred from the results of the single salt experiments, we also examined the structural transformations of the Fe_xN and its reactivity after being exposed to two

distinct groundwater samples.

3.5.1. Carbonate-rich groundwater

The Fe_xN aged for 30 days in GW_{HCO₃⁻}, characterized by high HCO₃⁻ (9.6 mM) and Mg²⁺ (5.2 mM) content (Table S1), exhibited major peaks of GR_{CO₃} and chukanovite in the XRD pattern (Fig. 5A and Table S7). SEM images demonstrate the presence of large aggregates formed by hexagonal (larger) and rhomboidal (smaller) sheets ascribed to GR_{CO₃} and chukanovite, respectively (Fig. 5B). The corrosion products identified in GW_{HCO₃⁻} thus aligned well with those found in the HCO₃⁻ solutions. However, the extent of Fe_xN corrosion in GW_{HCO₃⁻} was substantially larger compared to that in the 10 mM HCO₃⁻ solution; while the Fe_xN NPs retained about 60 wt% of the γ'-Fe₄N crystalline phase in the single salt system, only 25 wt% of γ'-Fe₄N remained in the NPs aged in GW_{HCO₃⁻} (Tables S5 and S7). The accelerated Fe_xN corrosion in GW_{HCO₃⁻} can be attributed to combination of the high concentration of Mg²⁺ ions and the presence of NO₃⁻ (0.5 mM), based on the observations from the single salt experiments described in sections 3.4.2 and 3.3.5. The pH of GW_{HCO₃⁻} after Fe_xN aging was 8.9 (Table S2), which falls between the pH values observed for the single salt HCO₃⁻ (10 mM) and Mg²⁺ (5 mM) systems. The Fe_xN corrosion products identified in the Mg²⁺ single salt experiments, i.e., akaganite and white rust, were not detected in GW_{HCO₃⁻}. These results suggest that the corrosion behavior of the Fe_xN in GW_{HCO₃⁻} can be explained by an interplay of the effects of individual inorganic solutes. The nature of corrosion products was mainly influenced by the presence of HCO₃⁻, while Mg²⁺ and NO₃⁻ ions played a crucial role in accelerating the Fe_xN NP corrosion.

Although the presence of HCO₃⁻ was found to enhance the reactivity of the aged Fe_xN with TCE, the overall reactivity of the Fe_xN aged in GW_{HCO₃⁻} was lower than that of the Fe_xN NPs aged in UPW (Fig. 5C,

Table S2, and Fig. S5), with the *k*_{obs} value similar to that of the Fe_xN aged in a 5 mM Mg²⁺ solution. The overall suppressing effect of solutes in GW_{HCO₃⁻} on its reactivity can be mainly attributed to the enhanced Fe_xN corrosion, which resulted in the depletion of the reducing capacity and the reduced availability of the reactive sites for the contaminant reduction. Additionally, a groundwater analysis revealed the presence of dissolved organic carbon in GW_{HCO₃⁻} at a concentration of 2.9 mg/L (Table S1). Although this concentration was relatively low, a reduction in the rate of TCE degradation by nZVI-based NPs has previously been observed at humic acid concentrations as low as 5 mg/L due to the adsorption of the humic acid onto the active sites of the surfaces of the NPs [36,69,70]. Therefore, a minor contribution of dissolved natural organics to the observed reactivity decrease cannot be completely ruled out.

3.5.2. Groundwater contaminated by NO₃⁻

The Fe_xN aged in GW_{NO₃⁻} underwent complete oxidation with GR_{CO₃} as the dominant (54.1 wt%) reaction product (Fig. 5A and Table S7). An XRD pattern further revealed the presence of calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) polymorphs aragonite (36.5 wt%) and calcite (9.4 wt%). Considering the relatively high concentrations of Ca²⁺ (7.2 mM) and HCO₃⁻ (6.2 mM) in this groundwater sample (Table S1), the increase in the pH during Fe_xN corrosion from 7.5 to 8.8 (Table S2) shifted the carbonate equilibrium in favor of the poorly soluble CaCO₃, leading to the precipitation of these minerals. SEM images of the aged Fe_xN NPs showed aggregates with well-developed hexagonal platelets, which had a typical carbonate green rust morphology (Fig. 5D). The dominant presence of GR_{CO₃} as the corrosion product can be explained by the relatively high HCO₃⁻ concentration in GW_{NO₃⁻}. GR_{CO₃} was identified as the only Fe_xN oxidation product in the 4 mM HCO₃⁻ solution (see section 3.3.3). The extensive

Fig. 5. Characteristics of Fe_xN NPs aged in carbonate-rich (GW_{HCO₃⁻}) and NO₃⁻-impacted (GW_{NO₃⁻}) groundwater samples: (A) XRD patterns, (B) SEM image of NPs aged in GW_{HCO₃⁻}, (C) TCE reduction rate constants for aged NPs, (D) SEM image of NPs aged in GW_{NO₃⁻}. GR_{CO₃}: carbonate green rust, CV: chukanovite, AR: aragonite, C: calcite.

corrosion of Fe_xN NPs in GW_{NO₃⁻} can be attributed to the presence of NO₃⁻ (2.6 mM) in excess to the Fe_xN reducing capacity (1.6 times). The NO₃⁻ ions present in GW_{NO₃⁻} most likely originated from the intrusion of fertilized-impacted water into the underlying aquifer. NO₃⁻ underwent reduction through the Fe_xN, thereby accelerating the Fe_xN corrosion and depleting the NP reducing capacity, leading to the complete oxidation of the Fe_xN NPs in GW_{NO₃⁻}.

Only marginal TCE removal was observed in the degradation experiments (Fig. 5C, Table S2, and Fig. S5), which can be attributed to TCE adsorption onto corrosion products and/or potential TCE reductive dechlorination onto the GR_{CO₃} surface [57,58]. Interestingly, surface passivation did not occur until the Fe_xN NPs were fully oxidized. This differs from the single salt NO₃⁻ experiments, where a fraction of non-oxidized γ'-Fe₄N phase remained, even when NO₃⁻ was present in excess (1.25–3.1 times the Fe_xN reducing capacity; see section 3.3.5). The likely reason for this discrepancy is the lower pH of the Fe_xN suspension in GW_{NO₃⁻} (8.8 compared to ≈10 in the NO₃⁻ experiments, Table S2). The lower pH suppressed the formation of a stable thin layer of iron (oxyhydr)oxides on the NP surface, which would otherwise have inhibited the electron transfer from the NP core to the adsorbed species. Overall, the experiments conducted in GW_{NO₃⁻} demonstrate that the efficacy of the Fe_xN NPs in TCE dechlorination can be severely diminished in environments with high NO₃⁻ concentrations, such as waters impacted by fertilizers.

3.5.3. Implications for the fate, reactivity, and safety of Fe_xN NPs in groundwater remediation

Fe_xN NPs undergo gradual corrosion in a water environment, resulting in the formation of various iron-containing mineral phases, including oxides, hydroxides, oxyhydroxides, green rusts, and phosphates. These corrosion products are non-toxic and naturally occurring in the environment. As demonstrated in previous research, the corrosion rate of Fe_xN NPs is considerably slower than that of pristine nZVI [17, 18]. This leads to the extended reactive lifetime of Fe_xN NPs and enhanced electron selectivity in contaminant degradation. However, certain groundwater solutes, particularly NO₃⁻ and HPO₄²⁻, can adversely affect the reactivity and longevity of Fe_xN NPs, as shown and discussed above.

In addition to forming iron-containing minerals, Fe_xN NPs release nitrogen into the groundwater over time, primarily as ammonia [17]. While excessive ammonia leaching could pose a risk to nearby surface waters, its gradual release at low levels (<0.5 g/L) into groundwater could be advantageous in certain remediation contexts. Specifically, it could enhance biotic degradation of chlorinated ethenes stimulating dechlorination by *Dehalococcoides* [74]. To minimize environmental risks, it is advisable to conduct a comprehensive site inspection and groundwater flow modeling before application. These evaluations should confirm that leaching of both Fe_xN NPs and ammonia into surface waters will not occur. With an appropriate site assessment, the application of Fe_xN NPs for groundwater cleanup is expected to pose minimal environmental risks.

3.5.4. Limitations of predicting corrosion phenomena using single salt systems

Our results show that single salt experiments are valuable for predicting the fate and reactivity of Fe_xN NPs in complex environmental media. The structural changes of Fe_xN NPs in real groundwater samples could be well explained by an interplay of the effects of major inorganic solutes. The reactivity of aged NPs with TCE followed similar trends to those observed in single salt experiments, although Fe_xN NPs aged in GW_{HCO₃⁻} were less reactive than expected, considering their high reactivity in HCO₃⁻ solutions. It should be taken into account that the effects of individual solutes are not always additive, and their mutual interactions cannot be entirely predicted from single salt experiments. This may lead to the underestimation of the passivation processes in real environments. Previous studies on (n)ZVI-based particles also found that

the *k*_{obs} values for TCE reduction in real groundwater were somewhat lower than those predicted by single salt systems [28,35,36]. This discrepancy was attributed to the effects of minor groundwater constituents and variations in pH values and ionic strength, which may have influenced the particle corrosion processes and reactivity.

Additionally, the presence of dissolved oxygen is known to promote corrosion and surface passivation of Fe-bearing NPs [43]. Although this study has not addressed this phenomenon, corrosion processes under oxic conditions are particularly relevant in surface waters, shallow aquifers and aquifer recharge areas [71]. Therefore, assessing the influence of dissolved oxygen on the structural transformations and reactivity of Fe_xN NPs warrants further investigation.

4. Conclusion

The results of this study clearly demonstrate that aged Fe_xN NPs can effectively degrade TCE across a wide range of water compositions, with varying concentrations of Na⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Cl⁻, SO₄²⁻ and HCO₃⁻ ions. Typical corrosion products observed in these waters included white rust and green rust minerals. The generally small variations in TCE dechlorination rates among different single salt systems could be explained by the type and concentration of present groundwater solutes, nature of corrosion products, extent of Fe corrosion and pH levels. The fastest TCE dechlorination occurred when the Fe_xN NPs were aged in high concentrations of HCO₃⁻, with carbonate green rust being the predominant corrosion product. However, TCE degradation by Fe_xN NPs was strongly suppressed in waters containing HPO₄²⁻ and NO₃⁻ ions, suggesting lower efficacy of the Fe_xN-based treatment in groundwaters impacted by fertilizers. HPO₄²⁻ forms strong complexes and insoluble precipitates on the (n)ZVI surface, leading to the blocking of the active sites. By contrast, NO₃⁻ is reduced by (n)ZVI-based materials, which can lead to rapid surface passivation with a thick layer of iron (oxyhydr)oxides or even complete particle oxidation. Experiments in two groundwater samples validated the results obtained in single salt experiments. Comparison with previous research indicates that S-nZVI particles may be more prone to surface passivation in HPO₄²⁻-rich waters, compared to Fe_xN NPs, yet exhibit lower susceptibility to passivation in NO₃⁻-impacted waters. However, this assumption has yet to be meticulously investigated. The presented results can serve as a reference for predicting the performance of Fe_xN-based materials in the treatment of contaminated groundwater.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jana Krřezek Oborná: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Miroslav Brumovský:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Vesna Micić:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Josef Kašlík:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Investigation. **Jan Filip:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.jece.2025.115431](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2025.115431).

Data availability

The data underlying this study are openly available in Zenodo at <https://zenodo.org/records/14678966>.

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